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REVIEW OF THE EFFECTIVENESS OF STATINS TO PREVENT OF HYPERLIPIDEMIA IN PATIENTS UNDER 40

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Summary,

Hypercholesterolemia and statin treatment are now common among people over 65 years of age, but clinical heterogeneity in this increasing age group is wide, and treatment decisions may differ from those in younger patients. Statins are the cornerstone of prevention and treatment of atherosclerotic cardiovascular disease (ASCVD). The purpose is to discuss the presentation, modifying factors, and decisions about treating hypercholesterolemia with statins in older adults and overweight patients under 40 years of age, and to focus on primary prevention.

Key words: *statins, prevention, atherosclerosis, coronary heart disease, clinical pharmacology, effectiveness, safety.*

Relevance

There are no randomized controlled trials in people over 80 years of age at baseline. Randomized controlled trials in younger patients and subgroups over 65 years of age, as well as observational studies, support the effectiveness of treatment in the secondary prevention of atherosclerotic cardiovascular disease (ASCVD), but data from primary prevention trials are less clear. Available data do not indicate specific harm in elderly patients and, therefore, prudent primary prevention is possible. However, people over 65 years of age are a biologically very heterogeneous group with frequent frailty, comorbidities, and multiple concomitant medications. All of this, as well as personal preferences, must be taken into account when making treatment decisions. Treatment with statins is just one way to prevent ASCVD in older adults. Treatment for hypercholesterolemia should begin well before age 80, and there is no need to stop statin treatment solely because of chronological age. After 75 years of age, treatment should begin

in patients with ASCVD and primary prevention should be considered prudently. As with any prophylaxis, statin treatment should be discontinued when palliative treatment is initiated. Ongoing and planned studies involving more than 70 participants will provide more information about primary prevention in older adults [8, 20, 32].

Over the past decade, several drugs have been developed to treat dyslipidemia. Inclisiran, a small interfering RNA targeting proprotein convertase subtilisin / kexin type 9 (PCSK9), shows effects comparable to those of the PCSK9 monoclonal antibody. Bempedoic acid, an ATP citrate lyase inhibitor, is a valuable treatment option for patients intolerant to statins. Pemafibrate, the first selective proliferator-activated receptor alpha modulator peroxisomes, showed a favorable benefit-risk balance in a phase 2 study, but a large phase 3 clinical trial (PROMINENT) was recently stopped due to futility based on a late interim analysis. High doses of icosapent-ethyl, a modified eicosapentaenoic acid preparation, have beneficial effects on the cardiovascular system. Evinacumab, an angiotensin-like type 3 (ANGPTL3) monoclonal antibody, reduces plasma LDL cholesterol in patients with refractory hypercholesterolemia. New antisense oligonucleotides targeting apolipoprotein C3 (apoC3), ANGPTL3, and lipoprotein(a) significantly reduced levels of their target molecules, with beneficial effects on comorbid dyslipidemias. Apolipoprotein A1 (apoA1) is considered a potential treatment to exploit the atheroprotective effects of high-density lipoprotein cholesterol (HDL-C), but convincing clinical evidence is needed [1, 12, 27].

Population aging is a global trend, and older adults have a higher risk of atherosclerotic cardiovascular disease (ASCVD) and related mortality. Statins have been observed to reduce cardiovascular events in patients with ASCVD. However, compared with secondary prevention in the elderly, the benefit of statins for primary prevention in people younger than 40–45 years of age is greater [2, 19, 33].

In a study from Taiwan University, patients aged 65 years or younger were identified without a history of cardiovascular disease. New statin users were matched 1:4 with statin non-users based on certain variables. The risks of major adverse cardiovascular events (MACE) and all-cause mortality were estimated using Cox proportional hazards models [2, 24, 31].

statin users were selected ; the mean age was 61.3 years, and 63% were women. At a mean follow-up of 4.8 years, statin use was associated with a reduced risk of MACE (hazard ratio [HR]: 0.75; 95% confidence interval [CI] 0.52–0.98) and mortality (HR: 0.72 , 95% CI: 0.55–0.93) adjusted for time-varying LDL cholesterol levels. No significant differences in effect were found between subgroups [2, 13, 36].

More than 15 years have passed since the effectiveness of statins in the secondary prevention of coronary artery disease was first proven in a prospective randomized Scandinavian study involving 4444 patients with stable angina and/or a history of myocardial infarction with elevated plasma levels of total cholesterol and LDL. Taking simvastatin at a dose of 20-40 mg/ day for 5 years significantly reduced overall mortality by 30%, cardiovascular mortality by 42%, the incidence of acute coronary events by 34%, and the need for myocardial revascularization procedures by 37%. . Since then, all major clinical trials (CARE , LIPID , WOSCOPS , AFCAPS / TexCAPS , HPS , ASCOT-LLA, CARDS) have shown that continuous use of statins for 3-6 years reduces the risk of MI, unstable angina and death. by 25-40%, ischemic strokes – by 25-30%. These impressive results are associated with reductions in total cholesterol and LDL cholesterol by 25-30 and 30-35%, respectively [5, 10].

Until recently, the prognostic value of lowering cholesterol levels in patients with hypertension was unknown. In the ASCOT-LLA study, which examined the effectiveness of atorvastatin at a dose of 10 mg in patients with hypertension and risk factors for the development of coronary artery disease, initially with normal or moderately elevated levels of total cholesterol (cholesterol <6.5 mmol/l, plasma triglycerides <4.5 mmol/ l), the drug significantly reduced the total risk of non-fatal MI and death from coronary heart disease by 36% (primary endpoint), the total risk of cardiovascular complications and the need for myocardial revascularization - by 21%, the risk of coronary complications - by 29%, and strokes – by 27% and the occurrence of unstable angina – by 41%. It has become clear that in patients with hypertension it is necessary to use statins to prevent cardiovascular complications [7, 16, 28].

Thus, according to the results of strictly planned large randomized clinical trials, the indications for prescribing statins for primary and secondary prevention of cardiovascular

diseases, including coronary heart disease and ischemic stroke, were significantly expanded [6, 22, 35].

The effectiveness of lipid-lowering interventions using statins in the primary and secondary prevention of cardiovascular diseases was greatest in patients who achieved the target LDL-C level, which in 2001 was defined for patients with an established diagnosis of coronary artery disease below 100 mg%, or 2.6 mmol/l. Recent international recommendations for the diagnosis and correction of lipid metabolism disorders for the purpose of preventing and treating atherosclerosis note that if dietary measures do not lead to normalization of lipid parameters, all patients with coronary artery disease should be prescribed statins with a target reduction in LDL-C levels of less than 2.5 mmol / l (100 mg%), and the choice of drug and its dose depend on the lipid profile. The most convincing clinical need to achieve the target level of LDL cholesterol in patients with coronary artery disease was confirmed by the results of the GREACE clinical trial. The purpose of this work was to study the effect of atorvastatin in patients with coronary artery disease in doses of 10-80 mg with the obligatory achievement of the target LDL-C level in comparison with a group of patients in whom the doses were not titrated when prescribing statins, which corresponds to the currently common practice of managing patients with hypercholesterolemia. This prospective, open-label study included 1600 outpatients with a verified diagnosis of coronary artery disease and an LDL cholesterol level > 2.6 mmol/l, or 100 mg/dl, after a 6-week period of a lipid-lowering diet. The duration of treatment was 3 years [14, 26].

Recently, data have been obtained on the need to use statins in groups at high risk of coronary artery disease, diabetes, etc. in patients with “normal” cholesterol levels. The new target level of LDL cholesterol in patients with coronary artery disease at high risk of complications and the expansion of indications for the use of lipid-lowering therapy require increasing the effectiveness of this type of treatment. The objectives can be solved by using statins with a pronounced lipid-lowering effect in large doses or their combination with other lipid-modifying drugs. Statins are one of the safest classes of drugs, treatment with them is well tolerated. Although statins have been proven to be well tolerated in all controlled studies and over 20 years of experience, in new conditions their safety is attracting increased

attention. The most significant side effects of statins are toxic effects on the liver and muscle tissue. The frequency of a more than 3-fold increase in liver transaminase activity during treatment is about 1%, which is the same for almost all statins, and depends on the dose of the drug. In case of increased transaminase activity, stop taking statins; the level of liver enzymes returns to normal within 2-3 months [3, 34].

According to a Russian multicenter epidemiological study examining the prevalence of risk factors for cardiovascular diseases in various regions of the Russian Federation - "ESSE-RF" (2014 г.), only 9.7% of patients with coronary heart disease (CHD) from 35 to 64 years old take statins, of which only 9.2% achieve target values of LDL cholesterol, i.e., less than 1% of even patients with coronary artery disease are treated according to recommendations, not to mention patients with high and, especially, moderate risk. However, in European countries the situation is also far from ideal. Thus, according to the results of a study in Denmark, a fifth of the population aged 35–100 years is undertreated with statins in accordance with the criteria of European recommendations, while 0.2% of people receive therapy aimed at lowering cholesterol levels without sufficient justification. In the same Denmark, 674 thousand cases of long-term use of statins were studied - 14% of patients stopped taking statins by the 6th month of treatment [11, 29].

The purpose of this article is to broadly review the most popular myths in order to give practicing physicians: cardiologists, internists, interventional cardiologists, neurologists, and general practitioners weapons to combat myths, thus increasing patient adherence to much-needed statin therapy [15].

The JUPITER study included 17,092 patients over 50 years of age (men) and 60 years of age (women) with no history of cardiovascular disease or diabetes mellitus (DM), LDL cholesterol levels <3.36 mmol/L and elevated high-sensitivity C-C levels. reactive protein (hs-CRP) (2 mg/l or more). The average LDL cholesterol level before treatment was 2.79 mmol/l. Patients were randomized to rosuvastatin 20 mg and placebo groups [18, 30].

Despite the fact that the study was planned for 5 years, it was stopped early due to a statistically significant positive result in the rosuvastatin group identified during the analysis. A 50% reduction in LDL-C and a 37% reduction in hs-CRP was associated with a 44% reduction in the risk of the primary endpoint (cardiovascular death, MI, stroke, any

revascularization , hospitalization for unstable angina) compared with placebo. The average level of LDL cholesterol during rosuvastatin therapy decreased to 1.43 mmol/l. The results of this study became a strong argument in favor of highly active statin therapy not only in secondary, but also in primary prevention [4, 26].

In 2016, the results of the HOPE-3 study were published, which included more than 12.5 thousand patients with a moderate risk of cardiovascular complications. Of these, 37% had hypertension, 13% had impaired glucose tolerance or fasting glycemia, 27% of participants smoked, just under 6% suffered from diabetes, 36% of cases had low levels of high-density lipoprotein cholesterol (HDL) and 26% – family history of coronary artery disease. The average level of total cholesterol was 5.2 mmol/l, LDL cholesterol – 3.3 mmol/l, median hs -CRP – 2.0 mg/l. Patients were prescribed a combination of an antihypertensive drug (candesartan + hydrochlorothiazide) and rosuvastatin 10 mg/ day ; in comparison groups, one or both drugs were replaced by placebo. At the same time, those receiving rosuvastatin at a dose of 10 mg had a 24% lower composite risk of myocardial infarction, stroke or cardiovascular death and a 25% lower risk of hospitalizations for cardiovascular diseases; the LDL cholesterol level decreased by an average of 22% (to 2.3 mmol/l), and hs -CRP – by 0.19 mg/l. The results of the study demonstrate the importance of prescribing statins to patients with moderate cardiovascular risk, calculated on the basis of clinical scores [7, 9].

Reducing the risk of complications of atherosclerosis in the elderly population is especially important, since this age group has the highest prevalence of cardiovascular disease or subclinical atherosclerosis and dyslipidemia is common. In a meta-analysis examining the relationship between cholesterol levels and vascular mortality, it was found that high cholesterol levels are a significant risk factor for death from coronary artery disease in all age groups, but in the older age group its effect is less. A decrease in total cholesterol levels by 1 mmol/l in people aged 40–49 years was associated with a more pronounced reduction in mortality from coronary heart disease (risk ratio 0.44) than in people aged 80–89 years (hazard ratio 0.85) [21].

A significant reduction in the risk of cardiovascular events during long-term statin therapy was demonstrated in the PROSPER study in patients over 65 years of age and

confirmed by data from a cohort analysis of the largest secondary prevention studies. In a meta-analysis Cholesterol Treatment Trialists' reduction in the incidence of major cardiovascular events was directly proportional to the absolute reduction in LDL cholesterol levels. The results of the Swedish MI Registry showed that statin treatment is associated with a reduction in cardiovascular mortality in older patients after MI, and, what is especially important to emphasize, without increasing the risk of developing cancer [6, 23].

Old age as such, and especially due to the significant number of comorbid diseases, as well as due to taking a large number of drugs that can interact with statins, is considered as a factor increasing the risk of developing undesirable effects of statins, which makes it safer to use drugs of this group at a young age in patients with increased body weight. When prescribing statins, it is recommended to start with small doses and, if necessary, slowly increase the dose under the monitoring of safety indicators [17, 31].

Conclusions

Conducted studies and many years of clinical experience have proven the effectiveness and safety of statins, both in the framework of secondary and primary prevention of atherosclerosis and related diseases. The choice of drug should be based on clinical trial data, taking into account the effectiveness and safety of long-term use, as well as the ability to achieve the target LDL-C level. With the introduction of statins into clinical practice, for the first time, a real opportunity arose to influence the development of atherosclerosis, which should be taken advantage of by a doctor interested in the effective and safe treatment of patients.

You can also note the importance of using statins at a young age in people with increased body weight for the primary prevention of atherosclerosis, since studies have shown that laboratory cholesterol levels return to normal after 12 weeks of study. It can be assumed that by switching to proper nutrition and gradually reducing body weight to average numbers, as well as by taking statins for a longer period of time, the risk of cardiovascular diseases will significantly decrease, naturally, with constant monitoring of biochemical blood parameters.

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